

POLICY BRIEF COMMON TEMPLATE

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

INTRODUCTION: PROJECT TITLE AND PROJECT OBJECTIVES

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02

(Developing and consolidating the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership (2021))

TOPIC: Ensuring Local Needs & Strengthening Distributed Infrastructures: OPERAS National Nodes

PROJECT: On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure (OPERAS-PLUS)

<https://operas-eu.org>

PROJECT: objectives

The general objective of the OPERAS-PLUS project is to provide the necessary support OPERAS needs to complete its preparatory phase and to transition its status into an ERIC.

This general objective is divided into several specific objectives (SOs), defined by the topic description, the recommendations provided by the ESFRI report and the issues raised by the OPERAS General Assembly in 2021:

(SO1) To develop and strengthen OPERAS' governance structure, especially financial, legal, and human resource management aspects of the infrastructure central hub in a sustainable way, compliant with research infrastructure (RI) management best practices.

(SO2) To support the establishment and development of OPERAS National Nodes; to establish and manage their relations with the central hub.

(SO3) To develop OPERAS' portfolio of services by providing both the required technology and a monitoring system for service development.

(SO4) To maximise OPERAS' impact in the ERA and at the international level by extending it beyond its current scope and onboarding new members and countries in the infrastructure.

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POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

● Implementation of research infrastructures.

National Nodes are essential structural elements within the OPERAS RI, serving as key connection points between European-level coordination and local research communities. These nodes ensure that local needs and perspectives are integrated into broader European initiatives, thus facilitating the internationalisation of research without losing diverse cultures, languages and traditions of scholarly practices.¹ This integration is fundamental for building a truly inclusive and effective European Research Area (ERA), particularly in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

¹ The importance of national contact points are common in a lot of European structures, as well as in [Horizon Europe](#) itself.

National Nodes are instrumental in delivering OPERAS' objectives and successful community management. To guide their development, an **OPERAS National Nodes Roadmap** was developed during the OPERAS-PLUS project, setting out four strategic principles:

- **Increasing awareness of OPERAS nationally;**
- **Building strong networks among relevant stakeholders;**
- **Understanding the specific needs of potential partners;**
- **Tailoring the dissemination of OPERAS services to meet those needs.**

The project has achieved critical milestones and key results that bring OPERAS closer to full operational maturity:

- Established a structured network of emerging National Nodes in 13 countries;
- Developed a common strategic framework for community engagement and service dissemination;
- Enhanced national visibility of OPERAS through targeted outreach and stakeholder involvement;
- Initiated collaboration with local institutions, laying the groundwork for long-term partnerships.

These results provide a solid foundation for the sustainable implementation of the National Nodes and demonstrate their potential to serve as multipliers of European impact at national and regional levels.

Despite the progress made, the **primary bottleneck remains a lack of sustained funding** for the National Nodes. Currently, most activities are carried out as in-kind contributions, placing a strain on institutional resources, slowing the response times for activity and limiting the Nodes' capacity to scale up their operations.

- **Access to research infrastructures.**

National Nodes facilitate bidirectional integration. This approach ensures that specific local needs are acknowledged, discussed, and integrated into the OPERAS infrastructure at the European level, while overarching recommendations, resources, and services are tailored to the unique needs of each national research community, fostering both scalability and collaboration.

Examples of the work and impact of OPERAS National Nodes within their respective countries can be grouped into:

- **Enhancing the visibility and reach of national initiatives and services**

The Peer Review Information Service for Monographs (PRISM), operated by OAPEN (representing OPERAS-NL in the Netherlands) on behalf of the DOAB became part of the OPERAS service catalogue in 2019. This integration allowed for migration to improved software, enhancing user experience and expanding outreach to a broader audience. It also helped OPERAS and the National Nodes to promote the service more effectively. For example, OPERAS-GER, led by the Max Weber Foundation, raised awareness of PRISM in Germany, leading to 25 new publisher supporters and over 1.3 million downloads. Furthermore, a service-level agreement allowed the OAPEN Library to host DFG-funded (Germany's largest research funding body) open access books.

- **Internationalisation & strengthening collaboration within national infrastructures**

The rapid establishment of OPERAS-IT (Italy) within 12 months initiated strong national engagement and led to the formation of H2IOSC, a collaborative cluster of humanities-focused infrastructures including CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, and OPERAS-IT.

OPERAS-GER (Germany) has become a key player in Germany's national research infrastructure through its involvement in the NFDI, especially the Text+ consortium, and by joining GKFI e.V. alongside CLARIN and DARIAH. It has also facilitated the integration of services such as BASE and the German National Library into the GoTriple platform, expanding access to millions of OA publications.

OPERAS-SI (Slovenia) was launched in December 2024 and now leads national efforts on publishing quality and visibility, supported by a broad open science community and expected future ministry funding.

→ Triggering new discussions

OPERAS-PL (Poland), led by IBL-PAN, developed the 'Manifesto of Open Humanities', stimulating national debate on integrating open science into research assessment and policy.

OPERAS-HR (Croatia), led by the University of Zadar, is aligning national standards with European developments by implementing services like PRISM and promoting initiatives locally, such as the Barcelona Declaration.

OPERAS-PT (Portugal), led by the University of Coimbra, contributes expertise on multilingualism and launched Mondaecus, a translation service supporting high-quality, collaborative scholarly translations. Across National Nodes, early translation efforts and services like GoTriple and VERA – available in eleven and nine languages, respectively – enhance accessibility and engagement with open scholarly communication across Europe.

● **Funding of research infrastructures.**

As OPERAS moves towards becoming an ERIC, different national funding models are being discussed within the Board of Governing Representatives, taking into account each country's GDP.

Securing sustainable funding is crucial for National Nodes to actively support the local implementation of OPERAS services in order to identify potential new members and enhance awareness in each country. **Investing in the National Nodes is not just an investment in OPERAS but in the future of open scholarly communication and research excellence in the ERA for Social Sciences and Humanities.**

● **Sustainability of research infrastructures.**

To sustain the impact of the National Nodes, to ensure they effectively contribute to national and EU priorities and maintain interconnectivity between infrastructures and research communities within SSH across the ERA, we recommend the following actions:

1. **Establish a Structured EU-Level Dialogue**

Encourage continuous engagement amongst the European Commission, OPERAS, and National Nodes to align strategies and explore collaboration opportunities for long-term sustainability.

2. **Foster Strategic Partnerships**

In recognition of the value that OPERAS National Nodes bring to the EU, key areas and actors identified nationally, particularly within the SSH, should be taken into account in EU policies to maximise impact.

3. **Enhance Financial Support at the EU Level**

Develop dedicated EU funding instruments to support the operational activities and coordination of National Nodes – especially staffing and service implementation – and encourage Member States to co-invest through ERIC membership or complementary national schemes.

By working together, we can strengthen the National Nodes and reinforce their pivotal role in achieving the connection between the European and national infrastructures.

